

Deciphering Venusian Polygonal Patterns: Exploring Potential Clues to Climate Change Dynamics

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Abstract

Venus has a geologically young surface. Morphological and spatial patterns and surface conditions are challenging due to high temperature, pressure, and relative atmosphere. Planetary heat loss caused deformation. Wrinkle ridges are found on Venus and also on other terrestrial planets. Wrinkle ridges provide information about orientations of shallow crustal stresses. In Venus, wrinkle ridges are associated with polygonal features indicating more recent resurfacing or regional stress.

Reference :

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